

Informed Consent Form (ICF)

The information listed below is being provided for your voluntary participation in this study. The information obtained will be analyzed together with that of other research participants, ensuring the confidentiality of the information obtained during the work. Furthermore, I declare that I authorize the anonymous disclosure of the transcript of my interview in the context of the research entitled "ReqCluster4IoT: A clustering method for functional requirements in Internet of Things applications".

This transcript adheres to the participants' privacy guidelines as outlined in the Informed Consent Form. Researchers maintain the privacy of participants regarding personal information such as name, initials, place of work, and country. This transcript will be available in an open access repository (such as Zenodo, FigShare, Github, and others).

OBJECTIVE: To investigate the perception of the results found by ReqCluster4IoT, based on an intuitive perspective of Requirements Engineers and IoT software Developers.

PROCEDURES: Participants will take part in a focus group using Google Meet, with questions related to the results obtained by ReqCluster4IoT, through the application of a proposed software.

VOLUNTEER: The volunteer participant will be accompanied by at least one researcher, and the researchers can clarify any doubts about the research/focus group using the contact information available at the end of this document.

PARTICIPANT PRIVACY: The researchers guarantee confidentiality regarding the information obtained, thus maintaining the privacy of the participants.

WITHDRAWAL: The research volunteer will have the freedom to withdraw from participation at any time, even if the work is in its final phase.

DISCOMFORT or RISKS: The following intellectual and emotional risks may be reported during the interview if the participant notices any of the following conditions and, at their discretion, immediately interrupts participation: feelings of embarrassment, discomfort, fear, shame, stress, and fatigue.

REIMBURSEMENT OR COMPENSATION: There are no personal expenses to participate in this study, nor is there any financial compensation, as the research does not imply any burden on participants.

THE RESEARCH: The researcher will treat your identity with professional standards of confidentiality and integrity. The research results will be available to you when completed. Your name or material indicating participation will not be disclosed without your permission.

I declare that I have been informed of the objectives of this work in a clear and detailed manner and that my doubts have been clarified. I know that I can request further information and change my decision to participate at any time, if I so wish.

If you have any questions, please contact us by email: bruno.carvalho1@discente.ufma.br and davi.viana@ufma.br

* Indicates required question

1. Email: *

2. Do you agree to this Free and Informed Consent Form? *

Mark only one oval.

I agree

I disagree

Characterization Form

3. What is your main educational background? *

Mark only one oval.

High School

Graduate

Master

Doctoral

4. Do you have experience with requirements analysis? *

Mark only one oval.

1 - based solely on academic knowledge

2 - based on academic knowledge and one project

3 - based on more than one project and up to six months of professional work

4 - based on more than one year of professional work

5. Do you have experience in software development? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1 - only academic knowledge
- 2 - academic knowledge and one project
- 3 - more than one project and up to six months of professional work
- 4 - more than one year of professional work

6. Do you have knowledge of IoT? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1 - only academic knowledge
- 2 - academic knowledge and one project
- 3 - more than one project and up to six months of professional work
- 4 - more than one year of professional work

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